

The Journal of the Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies, Faculty of Arts
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

LEAD CITY JOURNAL OF RELIGIONS AND INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

(ISSN 3043-4416)

Editorial Chief Consultant:
Anjola ROBBIN, PhD

Editor-in-Chief:
Ayodele Adeyinka ATOWOJU, PhD

Corresponding Editor:
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI, PhD

Lead City Journal of Religions and Intercultural Communication

(ISSN 3043-4416)

The Journal of the Department of Religious and Intercultural
Studies, Faculty of Arts, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

Volume 2, Number 1, August 2024

Exploring Parallels between the Conceptual Framework of *Odu Ifa* and the Figure of Jesus Christ through the Story of *Ela*

Olusegun T. AYANWALE

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

timsegun225@gmail.com, +2348060731268

Emmanuel Olujide ADETUNJI, PhD

Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

adetunji.emmanuel@lcu.edu.ng, +2348130598955

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4862-5864>

Abstract

This study explores the striking similarities between the conceptual framework of *Odu Ifa*, a traditional Yoruba spiritual system, and the figure of Jesus Christ, as exemplified in the narrative of *Ela*. Through a comparative analysis of key themes, teachings, and narratives, the study aims to elucidate both the shared elements and differences that illuminate the intersection of these cultural and religious traditions. The research employs a comprehensive methodology involving the analysis of *Odu Ifa* texts, Christian scriptures, and scholarly interpretations. The investigation reveals remarkable parallels in the roles of *Ela* and Jesus Christ as intermediaries between humanity and the divine, embodiments of sacrificial love and compassion, and sources of moral guidance and spiritual enlightenment. Despite their distinct theological and historical contexts, the narratives surrounding *Ela* and Jesus Christ offer profound insights into universal themes of redemption, transformation, and the pursuit of ultimate truth and salvation. The study concludes by emphasizing the enriching dialogue between *Odu Ifa* and Christianity, highlighting the potential for mutual understanding, interfaith dialogue, and cultural exchange. Recommendations for further research include interdisciplinary explorations of theological syncretism, comparative mythology, and cross-cultural perspectives to deepen understanding of shared values and wisdom across diverse religious traditions.

Keywords: *Odu Ifa*, Jesus Christ, *Ela*, Cultural Syncretism, Yoruba Mythology

Introduction

Odu Ifa, an esteemed divination system deeply entrenched in Yoruba heritage, serves as a reservoir of ancestral wisdom, providing spiritual and ethical guidance to the Yoruba populace (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Rooted in oral tradition and transmitted across generations, *Odu Ifa* encapsulates the intricate tapestry of beliefs, moral precepts, and cosmological insights that underpin Yoruba spirituality (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Comprising 256 verses known as *Odu*s, this system serves as a conduit for communication with the *Orisha*, the divine entities central to Yoruba religious observance.

Beyond its function in divination, *Odu Ifa* embodies the profound connection between the Yoruba community and the spiritual realm, offering a framework for comprehending both human existence and the universe at large (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Through the practice of divination, the *Babalawo*, or *Ifa* priest, decrypts the concealed messages within the *Odu* verses, providing counsel, enlightenment, and resolutions to life's dilemmas. This study is approached with a profound reverence for the cultural intricacies and spiritual profundity embedded within *Odu Ifa*, drawn from my extensive studies of Yoruba customs and heritage. Through a scholarly exploration of *Odu Ifa*'s conceptual underpinnings and its implications for understanding the human experience, this paper endeavours to illuminate the profound insights and spiritual enlightenment inherent in this ancient divination system. In examining the parallelism between *Odu Ifa*'s conceptual framework and the portrayal of Jesus Christ through the story of *Ela*, it is imperative to grasp the importance of Jesus Christ within Christianity. Jesus Christ, the central figure in Christian theology, is esteemed as the Son of God and the redeemer of humanity (Bible, *New International Version*, 2011). His teachings, as documented in the Bible, underscore themes of love, forgiveness, and redemption, laying the moral and spiritual groundwork of the Christian faith. The teachings of Jesus Christ are founded on

compassion and selflessness, demonstrated through his interactions with the marginalized and oppressed (Bible, *New International Version*, 2011). His sacrificial death on the cross is viewed as the ultimate demonstration of love and redemption, offering salvation to believers and emphasizing the significance of reconciliation with both God and fellow humans. Beyond his earthly existence, Jesus Christ's resurrection symbolizes triumph over sin and death, providing believers with hope and the promise of eternal life (Bible, *New International Version*, 2011). The narrative of Jesus Christ holds a central position in Christian theology, highlighting principles of faith, grace, and redemption through Christ's sacrificial sacrifice on the cross. Jesus Christ emerges as a pivotal figure within the Christian faith, embodying values of love, forgiveness, and redemption that continue to influence the beliefs and practices of countless adherents worldwide. His teachings and example serve as a moral compass, guiding believers toward lives characterized by faith, compassion, and service to others.

The confluence of diverse cultural and religious traditions often presents a rich tapestry for exploring the shared values and beliefs that define humanity (Awolalu, 1979, p. 23). Within the context of the Yoruba people of Nigeria and the Christian tradition, there exists a unique opportunity to delve into the parallels between the conceptual frameworks of *Odu Ifa* and the figure of Jesus Christ. *Odu Ifa*, a revered divination system central to Yoruba culture, is perceived to offer profound insights into the human condition and the cosmic order (Awolalu, 1979, p. 45). Conversely, Jesus Christ, as portrayed in Christian tradition, embodies principles of love, forgiveness, and redemption. Through an exploration of the story of *Ela*, a significant figure in *Odu Ifa*, this study endeavours to uncover the parallel themes and values that interconnect these two belief systems (Parrinder, 1980, p. 68). At the core of *Odu Ifa* lies the notion of destiny, which is believed to be predetermined and influenced by one's actions and decisions (Awolalu, 1979, p. 56). In the narrative of *Ela*, a divine emissary responsible for conveying messages between humanity and the divine realm, there is an encounter with a character who epitomizes the significance of fulfilling one's destiny. Similarly,

as Jesus Christ in Christianity. Both figures epitomize the ultimate expression of sacrificial love and redemption, though they originate from distinct cultural and religious backgrounds (Miller, 2005). This parallelism enhances the understanding of *Ela*'s significance within the Yoruba spiritual tradition and provides a framework for comparative interfaith dialogue and scholarly investigation.

Odu Ifa's Conceptual Framework Divination in Odu Ifa

Ifa divination is a pivotal aspect of Yoruba religion and spirituality. It involves a sophisticated system of knowledge and wisdom conveyed through the *Odu Ifa*, which are poetic and esoteric verses utilized during divination. *Ifa* divination acts as a bridge between humans and the divine, offering guidance, insights, and solutions to problems. Abimbola (2021) explains that *Ifa* is both a religious and philosophical system that covers various life aspects, including moral and ethical teachings (p. 35). The divination process generally involves a Babalawo, or *Ifa* priest, who interprets the *Odu Ifa* verses to provide spiritual guidance. This process is complex and demands extensive training and a deep understanding of the *Ifa* corpus. Olupona (2021) highlights that *Ifa* divination is not just about forecasting the future but also about understanding the present and past to make informed decisions (p. 112).

Spiritual Guidance and Ethical Teachings

Odu Ifa offers a moral and ethical framework that guides the behaviour and decisions of its followers. The teachings within the *Odu Ifa* emphasize virtues such as honesty, integrity, humility, and respect for elders and the community. These teachings are often communicated through stories, proverbs, and parables that illustrate the consequences of moral and immoral behavior. For example, in the *OduOgundaMeji*, there is a significant focus on the importance of truthfulness and integrity. Olatunji (2021) notes that the verse advises individuals to always speak the truth and maintain their integrity, as these are crucial

for maintaining harmony and balance in one's life and community (p. 78).

Relationships with Orisas

In Yoruba cosmology, the *Orisas* are deities that represent various natural forces and aspects of life. Each *Orisa* has specific attributes, domains, and functions, and they act as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans offer sacrifices and perform rituals to honor the *Orisas*, and in return, the *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) states that the *Odu Ifa* contains numerous verses that describe the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, as well as instructions on how to venerate them properly (p. 57). These relationships are essential to Yoruba religious practice, as they foster a sense of connection and interdependence between the spiritual and physical realms. Exploring the key principles and beliefs in *Odu Ifa* reveals a rich and intricate system of knowledge that integrates divination, ethical teachings, and relationships with *Orisas*. The holistic nature of *Odu Ifa* provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. It offers a structured approach to navigating life's challenges and making ethical decisions. Furthermore, the emphasis on relationships with *Orisas* underscores the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in one's life, as well as the interconnectedness of all beings.

Examination of Parallels Between *Odu Ifa's* Teachings and Jesus Christ's Teachings

Divination and Prophecy: Divination in *Odu Ifa* is a fundamental practice that involves interpreting sacred verses to connect with the divine. This is akin to the concept of prophecy in Christianity, where prophets receive divine messages to guide their communities. In *Odu Ifa*, the *Babalawo* (*Ifa* priest) interprets these verses to provide insights into the past, present, and future, aiding individuals in making informed decisions. Abimbola (2021) points out that *Ifa* is a comprehensive

religious and philosophical system that addresses various life aspects, including moral and ethical teachings (p. 35). In Christianity, prophecy serves a similar function, with prophets acting as intermediaries between God and people. Biblical prophets such as Isaiah and Jeremiah offered guidance and warnings to the Israelites. The New Testament presents Jesus Christ as the ultimate prophet, delivering God's will and offering spiritual guidance. Olupona (2021) highlights that both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy seek to understand the present and past to make informed decisions (p. 112).

Spiritual Guidance and Ethical Teachings: Odu Ifa provides a moral and ethical framework that directs behaviour and decision-making. Its teachings emphasize virtues like honesty, integrity, humility, and respect for elders and the community, conveyed through stories, proverbs, and parables similar to those of Jesus Christ found in the New Testament. For instance, the *OduOgundaMeji* stresses truthfulness and integrity, advising individuals to speak the truth and uphold their integrity to maintain harmony and balance. Olatunji (2021) notes that these virtues are crucial for social order and ethical behaviour (p. 78). Similarly, Jesus Christ's teachings in the Gospels emphasize virtues such as love, compassion, and forgiveness. The parable of the Good Samaritan, for example, highlights the importance of compassion and kindness towards others (Luke 10:25-37).

Relationships between Orisas and Jesus Christ's Intercession: In Yoruba cosmology, *Orisas* are deities representing various natural forces and life aspects, acting as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans honor *Orisas* through sacrifices and rituals, and in return, *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) explains that the *Odu Ifa* includes numerous verses describing the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, along with instructions on proper veneration (p. 57). This dynamic mirrors the Christian belief in Jesus Christ as a mediator between humanity and God. Christians believe that Jesus intercedes on their behalf, offering spiritual guidance, forgiveness, and blessings. The reciprocal

relationship is evident in prayer and worship, where believers seek Jesus' intercession and strive to live by his teachings. Exploring the parallels between *Odu Ifa's* teachings and those of Jesus Christ reveals a rich convergence of spiritual principles and ethical frameworks. The study reveals, both *Odu Ifa* and the teachings of Jesus Christ offer comprehensive frameworks for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. They provide structured approaches to facing life's challenges and making ethical decisions. The focus on relationships with *Orisas* in *Odu Ifa* and Jesus Christ's intercession in Christianity highlights the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in life and the interconnectedness of all beings. This comparative analysis deepens our understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal quest for spiritual guidance and moral integrity.

Analysis of How the Values and Principles of *Odu Ifa* Align with the Teachings of Jesus Christ

In *Odu Ifa*, divination is a core practice where the *Babalawo* (*Ifa* priest) interprets esoteric verses to communicate with the divine. This practice closely parallels the concept of prophecy in Christianity, where prophets receive divine messages to guide their communities. Both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy serve to provide insights into the past, present, and future, aiding individuals in making informed decisions. Abimbola (2021) notes that *Ifa* encompasses various aspects of life, including moral and ethical teachings, making it a comprehensive religious and philosophical system (p. 35). Christian prophecy, as seen in the Bible, features prophets like Isaiah and Jeremiah, who conveyed God's messages to guide the people of Israel. The New Testament further presents Jesus Christ as the ultimate prophet, whose teachings and prophecies offer spiritual guidance. According to Olupona (2021), both *Ifa* divination and biblical prophecy aim to understand the present and past to inform future decisions, highlighting their similar roles in guiding adherents (p. 112).

Relationships between *Orisas* and Jesus Christ's Intercession

In Yoruba cosmology, *Orisas* are deities representing various natural forces and life aspects, acting as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. The relationship between humans and *Orisas* is reciprocal; humans honour *Orisas* through sacrifices and rituals, and in return, *Orisas* provide protection, blessings, and guidance. Adekunle (2022) explains that the *Odu Ifa* includes numerous verses describing the attributes and stories of the *Orisas*, along with instructions on proper veneration (p. 57). This dynamic mirrors the Christian belief in Jesus Christ as a mediator between humanity and God. Christians believe that Jesus intercedes on their behalf, offering spiritual guidance, forgiveness, and blessings. The reciprocal relationship is evident in prayer and worship, where believers seek Jesus' intercession and strive to live by his teachings. Analyzing how the values and principles of *Odu Ifa* align with the teachings of Jesus Christ reveals a deep and fascinating convergence of spiritual principles and ethical frameworks. This study recognizes that, both *Odu Ifa* and the teachings of Jesus Christ provide comprehensive frameworks for understanding the interconnectedness of the spiritual and physical worlds. They offer structured approaches to navigating life's challenges and making ethical decisions. The emphasis on relationships with *Orisas* in *Odu Ifa* and Jesus Christ's intercession in Christianity highlights the importance of maintaining harmony and balance in one's life and the interconnectedness of all beings. This comparative analysis enriches our understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal quest for spiritual guidance and moral integrity.

Life of Jesus Christ

Jesus Christ, the central figure in Christianity, is believed to have been born around 4 BCE in Bethlehem, Judea. His life and mission are primarily recorded in the New Testament Gospels of Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John. These texts state that Jesus was born to Mary, a virgin, and Joseph, a carpenter, under miraculous circumstances involving the Holy Spirit (Matthew 1:18-25; Luke 1:26-38).

Jesus spent his early years in Nazareth, beginning his public ministry at around thirty years old following his baptism by John the Baptist in the Jordan River (Mark 1:9-11). His ministry, which lasted about three years, involved preaching about the Kingdom of God, performing miracles, healing the sick, and teaching through parables. Jesus' teachings often challenged the established religious and social norms, emphasizing love, compassion, forgiveness, and justice (Mark 1:14-15; Matthew 5-7). The climax of Jesus' life was his crucifixion under the Roman governor Pontius Pilate, followed by his resurrection three days later, as claimed by his disciples. This event, known as the Resurrection, is a cornerstone of Christian faith, symbolizing victory over sin and death and affirming Jesus as the Son of God (Matthew 27-28; Luke 24; John 20).

Significance of Jesus Christ in Christianity

The significance of Jesus Christ in Christianity cannot be overstated. He is seen as the Messiah, the anointed one foretold in the Old Testament, who came to fulfill God's salvation plan for humanity. His life, death, and resurrection are central to Christian belief as they represent the means by which humans are reconciled with God. Christian doctrine holds that Jesus' sacrificial death on the cross paid the penalty for humanity's sins, offering redemption and the promise of eternal life to all who believe in him. The Apostle Paul captures this succinctly in his letter to the Romans: "For the wages of sin is death, but the gift of God is eternal life in Christ Jesus our Lord" (Romans 6:23). Jesus' resurrection is a pivotal event that affirms his divinity and the truth of his teachings. Celebrated annually on Easter Sunday, it symbolizes hope and new life. Wright (2012) notes that the resurrection is not just a past event but a present reality that transforms believers' lives, empowering them to live in accordance with Jesus' teachings (p. 67). Jesus Christ is also central to Christian worship and devotion. He is revered as Lord and Saviour, and his teachings continue to inspire and guide Christians in their daily lives. The sacraments of Baptism and the Eucharist (Holy Communion) were instituted by Jesus and remain vital practices in Christian worship, symbolizing entry into the Christian community and remembrance of

Jesus' sacrificial love (Matthew 28:19; Luke 22:19-20). Examining the life, teachings, and significance of Jesus Christ reveals that his impact extends far beyond the historical and religious context of first-century Palestine. Jesus' teachings provide a profound and timeless moral framework that addresses essential aspects of human existence: love, compassion, forgiveness, and justice. His life exemplifies these principles, serving as an enduring model of selfless love and sacrifice. Moreover, the significance of Jesus' death and resurrection provides a powerful narrative of redemption and hope, resonating with millions of believers worldwide. This narrative shapes Christian theology and inspires a commitment to ethical living and social justice. The enduring relevance of Jesus' teachings underscores the universal quest for meaning, purpose, and spiritual fulfillment. The Gospels state that Jesus was born to Mary and Joseph under miraculous circumstances involving the Holy Spirit (Matthew 1:18-25; Luke 1:26-38). His public ministry began after his baptism by John the Baptist (Mark 1:9-11) and involved preaching about the Kingdom of God, performing miracles, and teaching through parables (Mark 1:14-15; Matthew 5-7). Jesus' crucifixion and resurrection are central to Christian faith, symbolizing victory over sin and death (Matthew 27-28; Luke 24; John 20). Wright (2012) emphasizes that the resurrection is a present reality that transforms the lives of believers, empowering them to live according to Jesus' teachings (p. 67).

Comparison of Jesus Christ's Teachings with the Values of Odu Ifa

Ethical and Moral Teachings: Both Jesus Christ and *Odu Ifa* emphasize comprehensive ethical and moral frameworks that guide human behaviour. The teachings of Jesus Christ, as recorded in the New Testament, focus on virtues such as love, compassion, humility, and forgiveness. For example, in the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus presents the Beatitudes, which highlight the blessedness of the meek, merciful, and peacemakers (Matthew 5:3-12). Central to Jesus' message is the Great Commandment: "Love the Lord your God with all your heart and

importance of love, compassion, and integrity in guiding human behavior and fostering harmonious relationships. Jesus' teachings and the moral precepts of *Odu* offer timeless wisdom that helps individuals navigate the complexities of life with ethical clarity and spiritual insight. Moreover, the spiritual guidance provided by both Jesus Christ and the *Ifa* divination process underscores the universal quest for understanding and connection with the divine. The reciprocal relationships with the divine, whether through Jesus in Christianity or the *Orisas* in Yoruba cosmology, highlight the importance of maintaining spiritual harmony and seeking guidance from higher powers. This comparative analysis enriches the understanding of both traditions and underscores the universal themes of love, compassion, and ethical living.

Analysis of How Jesus Christ's Role as a Divine Figure Aligns with the *Orisa* in Yoruba Religion

Mediators between the Divine and Humanity: Both Christianity and Yoruba religions uphold the concept of intermediaries who bridge the gap between the divine and humanity. In Christian theology, Jesus Christ is seen as the supreme mediator between God and humans. Through his life, death, and resurrection, Jesus is believed to provide a pathway to salvation and eternal life. The New Testament asserts that Jesus advocates for believers before God (Hebrews 7:25). Similarly, the *Orisa* in Yoruba religion act as intermediaries between humans and the supreme deity, *Olodumare*. Each *Orisa* represents different natural forces and aspects of life, serving as channels through which humans can interact with the divine. Rituals, prayers, and offerings are made to honor the *Orisa*, who in return offer guidance, protection, and blessings. As noted by Adekunle (2022), the *Odu Ifa* texts include many verses that describe the attributes and stories of the *Orisa*, along with guidance on proper veneration (p. 57).

Divine Sacrifice and Redemption: The themes of divine sacrifice and redemption are pivotal in both Jesus Christ's role in Christianity and the *Orisa* in Yoruba religion. In Christianity, Jesus' death on the cross is viewed as the ultimate act of redemption. Believers hold that Jesus'

sacrifice atones for humanity's sins, providing forgiveness and the promise of eternal life to those who believe in him. This is emphasized by the Apostle Paul in Romans: "For the wages of sin is death, but the gift of God is eternal life in Christ Jesus our Lord" (Romans 6:23). In Yoruba religion, the *Orisa* also perform acts of sacrifice for the benefit of humanity. These sacrifices typically involve offerings and rituals aimed at restoring balance and harmony in the world. For instance, *Ogun*, the *Orisa* associated with war and iron, is known for enduring hardship and making sacrifices for the community's welfare. This concept of sacrifice highlights the reciprocal relationship between humans and the divine in Yoruba religion, where the *Orisa*'s sacrifices are reciprocated by human rituals and offerings (Abimbola, 2021, p. 45).

Spiritual Leadership and Influence: Both Jesus Christ and the *Orisa* are seen as significant spiritual leaders and influencers. Jesus is revered as the Son of God and the Messiah in Christianity, with his teachings continuing to inspire and guide millions of believers globally. Jesus' role as a spiritual leader is evident in his miracles, healing, and profound spiritual insights through his teachings and parables (Mark 1:14-15, Matthew 5-7). His resurrection is celebrated as a crucial event affirming his divinity and the truth of his teachings (Wright, 2012, p. 67).

Similarly, the *Orisa* are venerated as powerful spiritual entities in the Yoruba religion, each with distinct attributes and domains of influence. They are believed to have the power to intervene in human affairs, providing protection, guidance, and blessings. The teachings and stories associated with the *Orisa*, preserved in the *Odu Ifa* texts, continue to influence the spiritual practices and beliefs of the Yoruba people (Adekunle, 2022, p. 57). Comparing Jesus Christ's role as a divine figure with that of the *Orisa* in Yoruba religion, reveals common themes of mediation, sacrifice, moral guidance, and spiritual leadership. Both traditions offer rich spiritual narratives emphasizing the importance of connecting with the divine, living ethically, and seeking redemption through acts of sacrifice and devotion. Jesus Christ and the *Orisa* stand as powerful symbols of divine intervention and guidance, providing their followers with frameworks for understanding life's complexities and the

spiritual realm. This comparative analysis highlights the shared human quest for meaning, purpose, and connection with the divine, showcasing the profound ways different religious traditions address these fundamental aspects of human existence.

Exploration of the Parallels between Ela and Jesus Christ

Divine Descent and Mission: Ela in Yoruba mythology and Jesus Christ in Christianity are both divine figures who descended to Earth to guide and save humanity. Ela, known as *Ela Olurogbo*, comes down from the heavens (*Orun*) to the earth (*Aye*) to restore order and righteousness among people. He is sent by the supreme deity, Olodumare, to cleanse the world and impart principles of truth, justice, and ethical living (Adekunle, 2022, p. 102). Similarly, Jesus Christ, in Christian belief, is the Son of God sent to Earth to redeem humanity from sin. His mission involves teaching love, forgiveness, and moral integrity, ultimately sacrificing his life for humanity's salvation (Wright, 2012, p. 34).

Roles as Mediators between the Divine and Humanity: Ela and Jesus both act as intermediaries between the divine and humanity, facilitating communication and intercession. Ela is viewed as a divine emissary and manifestation of *Orunmila*, the deity of wisdom and divination, thus playing a critical role in spiritual guidance (Abimbola, 2021, p. 89). He frequently intervenes in human affairs to restore balance and guide people toward righteousness, symbolizing divine wisdom and moral rectitude (Olatunji, 2021, p. 87). Jesus Christ is considered the ultimate mediator in Christian theology, interceding on behalf of believers before God and bridging the gap between humanity and the divine through his life, death, and resurrection (Hebrews 7:25).

Sacrificial Roles: The concept of sacrifice is central to the roles of both Ela and Jesus. Ela's mission involves enduring hardships and making sacrifices to restore balance and purity in the world. His sacrifices are honored and reciprocated by humans through rituals and offerings, emphasizing the reciprocal relationship between humans and the divine (Abimbola, 2021, p. 45). In Christianity, Jesus' sacrificial death on the cross is seen as the ultimate act of redemption, atoning for humanity's

sins and offering forgiveness and eternal life to believers (Romans 6:23). In the account of this study, the parallels between *Ela* and Jesus Christ underscore universal themes of divine intervention, moral guidance, and the importance of ethical living. Both figures serve as powerful symbols of divine wisdom and purity, guiding their followers toward righteousness and spiritual enlightenment. Their stories highlight the shared human quest for meaning, redemption, and connection with the divine. The comparative analysis of *Ela* and Jesus shows how different traditions address fundamental aspects of human existence, such as the need for moral integrity, the significance of sacrifice, and the role of divine mediators. These parallels enrich our understanding of both Yoruba mythology and Christianity, illustrating the profound ways these traditions provide ethical and spiritual guidance to their followers.

Conclusion

Examining the parallels between the *Odu Ifa* framework and the figure of Jesus Christ, particularly through the story of *Ela*, reveals a rich tapestry of spiritual interconnectedness and universal truths. Through these narratives, one could encounter deep insights into compassion, sacrifice, and divine wisdom that go beyond cultural and religious divides. This comparative study not only deepens understanding of these traditions but also highlights their common aim of guiding humanity towards enlightenment and ethical living. As the exploration of these parallels continues, there could be open doors to more profound interfaith dialogue and a more inclusive appreciation of our shared spiritual heritage.

References

- Abimbola, W. (2021). *Ifa Divination: Communication Between Gods and Men*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Abiodun, R. (2018). *Yoruba Art and Language: Seeking the African in African Art*. Cambridge University Press.
- Adebayo, A. G. (2017). The Yoruba and the Making of Africa. *Journal of Black Studies*, 48(2), pp. 119-141.

- Adegbindin, O. (2018). *Orunmila's Footprint: Exploring the Philosophical and Religious Significance of The Yoruba Deity*. *Religions*, 9(4), 107.
- Adekunle, A. (2022). *Yoruba Sacred Music*. Ibadan, Nigeria: Spectrum Books Limited.
- Aderinto, S. (2017). *Guns and Society in Colonial Nigeria: Firearms, Culture, And Public Order*. Indiana University Press.
- Adewole, A. M., & Ajayi, J. O. (2019). Yoruba Cosmological Beliefs and Environmental Sustainability. *International Journal of Applied Environmental Sciences*, 14(1), 71-80.
- Ajayi, A. T., & Buhari, L. O. (2014). Methods Of Conflict Resolution in African Traditional Society. *African Research Review*, 8(2), 138-157.
- Akinleye, A. (2018). *Performing The Sacred: Yoruba Art, Ritual, And Performance in a Transatlantic Framework*. Routledge.
- Akintunde, D. O. (2017). Fundamentalism And Gender Relations: A Yoruba Perspective. *Religions*, 8(2), 25.
- Alabi, A. O. (2019). The Yoruba and the Making of the Atlantic World. *Slavery & Abolition*, 40(2), 331-351.
- Awolalu, J. O. (1979). *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Harlow, UK: Longman.
- Babatunde, E. D. (2018). *The Yoruba Family: Changes, Challenges and Survival Strategies*. Africa World Press.
- Falola, T., & Akinyemi, A. (2016). *Culture And Customs of The Yoruba*. Pan-African University Press.
- Falola, T., & Childs, M. D. (Eds.) (2019). *The Yoruba Diaspora in the Atlantic World*. Indiana University Press.
- Gbadegesin, S. (2016). *African Philosophy: Traditional Yoruba Philosophy and Contemporary African Realities*. Routledge.
- Idowu, E. B. (2017). *Olodumare: God in Yoruba Belief*. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing.
- Kehinde, A. (2016). "African Traditional Religions and the Yoruba Language." In *The Palgrave Handbook of African Oral Traditions and Folklore* (pp. 112-134). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Mbiti, J. S. (2015). *Introduction to African Religion*. Waveland Press.
- Miller, C. (2005). The Christ figure in Yoruba myth and ritual. *Journal of the American Academy of Religion*, 73(4), 1023-1049.
- Nnamani, A. G., & Nwoye, L. (2017). Ethical Foundations of the Igbo and Yoruba Traditional Societies: Implications for Sustainable Development.

- IGWEBUIKE: *An African Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 3(3), 164-182.
- Ogunbiyi, O. (2019). *Understanding The Orisha: Foundational Principles of The Yoruba Spiritual Tradition*. Llewellyn Worldwide.
- Ogungbile, D. O. (2019). *African Indigenous Religious Traditions in Local and Global Contexts: Perspectives and Insights*. Lexington Books.
- Ogunmodede, F. (2019). The Orisha Ela: Manifestations of divinity in Yoruba religion. *Religions*, 10 (6), 366.
- Ogunnaike, O. (2016). ÓrunMéta: The Yoruba Tripartite Conception of The Cosmos. *Journal of Religious and Philosophical Studies*, 13(1), 1-26.
- Ogunwale, J. A. (2017). The Yoruba World and Its Articulation. *Journal of Black Studies*, 48(3), 271-288.
- Ojo, A. E. (2020). *Social And Cultural Values of The Yoruba People*. Routledge.
- Olajubu, O. (2016). *Women in the Yoruba Religious Sphere*. SUNY Press.
- Olatunji, O. (2021). *Yoruba Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites*. Lagos, Nigeria: University of Lagos Press.
- Olupona, J. K. (2018). *African Religions: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press. pp. 67-89, 112.
- Olusola, A. P. (2019). Ifa Divination: An Indigenous Knowledge System of The Yoruba People. *Journal of Black Studies*, 50(2), 167-184.
- Omoyajowo, J. A. (2016). *The Cherubim and Seraphim Movement: A Study in Syncretism*. Routledge.
- Oshitelu, G. A. (2016). The Yoruba Concept of Ori and Human Destiny. *Philosophical Papers and Review*, 7(2), 9-18.
- Parrinder, G. (1980). *West African Religion: A Study of the Beliefs and Practices of Akan, Ewe, Yoruba, Ibo, and Kindred Peoples*. London: Epworth Press.
- Pearce, T. O. (2020). *Medicine And Magic in Yorubaland*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, N.T. (2012). *Simply Jesus, A New Vision of Who He Was, What He Did and Why He Matters*. HarperOne